

An Indian Perspective on IPR and Cyber Law Issues

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Abstract

A resolution passed by the United Nations General Assembly (UNCITRAL) on January 30, 1997, established the Model Law on Electronic Commerce on International Trade Law; this resolution gave rise to the Information Technology Act of 2000. Cybercrime is one of the most rapidly growing global crimes. The Act tackles certain pressing concerns regarding technology misuse and has been successful in establishing a framework for cyberspace rules; nonetheless, other substantial gaps remain, such as those concerning intellectual property. Any piece of information or body of knowledge with monetary value is considered intellectual property. Intellectual property rights, which include copyright, patent, trademark, and design, are a collection of ideas, innovations, and creations. Intellectual property refers to products of the human mind. The Information Technology Act of 2000 has no mention of intellectual property protection, even though intellectual property infringement is one of the most difficult issues in cyberspace. Internet users can violate their domain names and copyright, yet the Trade Mark Act of 1999 and the Copy Right Act of 1957 say nothing about this. As a result, we lack the enforcement tools necessary to guarantee domain name protection online. It is now necessary for us to pass specific laws to safeguard intellectual property online.

Key words: Copyright infringement, Cybersquatting, Cyber law, Domain names, challenges involved & IPR Issues

Introduction

The benefits of computers and the internet are widely acknowledged, and they are ingrained in both contemporary business and commerce and society at large. Modern businesses greatly benefit from the usage of computers and the internet, and without these tools, society would not be able to run efficiently. However, using computers and the internet has led to a number of inevitable computer and internet misuses. This has been made feasible in particular by the fact that computer use has no geographical restrictions and can originate from any country. These days, e-commerce is highly common, particularly in the business world. When companies take advantage of e-commerce and the Internet, their products and services may quickly reach customers all over the globe. Unfortunately, this has created an environment where cybercrime can thrive.¹

The use of a computer for illegal purposes, either as a perpetrator or a victim, is known as cybercrime. The Information Technology Act, passed by the Indian government to combat cybercrime, gave digital signatures and electronic data legal weight. The Act lays the groundwork for the medium's ability to facilitate and safeguard electronic transactions. The United Nations Commission on International Trade Law's (UNCITRAL) model law on electronic commerce serves as its foundation, advocating for the replacement of paper with digital records.²

Intellectual property issues, however, are not addressed in any part of the IT Act, 2000. Examples of intellectual property include copyrights, geographical indications, integrated circuits, patents, trademarks, and copyrights. Domain name conflicts and online copyright infringement are two of the most important issues raised by the author of this piece.

Key features of the 2000 Information Technology Act

There are 94 sections and thirteen chapters in the Act. Chapters include topics such as digital signatures, electronic records and their security, responsibilities of subscribers to digital signature certificates, electronic records and their attribution, acknowledgment, and dispatch, cyber regulation appellate tribunal, offenses, and network service provider liabilities. Changes to the Indian Evidence Statute, the Reserve Bank of India Act, the Indian Penal Code, and the Bankers' Books Evidence Act are detailed in the four schedules of the act.³

This Act's three objectives are:

- I. In order to facilitate the harmonization of laws pertaining to non-paper forms of communication and data storage, the United Nations has emphasized that all states should favourably examine model laws when drafting or updating their own legislation. A response and subsequent action are required to this appeal.
- II. The goal is to legitimize the practices of electronic commerce, which includes methods of electronic data interchange and other forms of electronic communication that do away with the need for paper-based information storage and transfer.
- III. in order to facilitate the electronic filing of paperwork with government bodies; to improve the efficient provision of government services by means of reliable electronic records.⁴

The IT Act fails to cover a number of important topics, including cybersquatting (the illegal acquisition of domain names without permission), cybercafé regulation, e-commerce transaction taxes, foreign-origin websites hosting net pornography, spam (the practice of sending unsolicited commercial emails that invade people's online privacy), crimes perpetrated by foreign-origin websites, cyberstalking, jurisdiction in cyberspace, cyberdefamation, stamp duty of e-contracts, etc.

Types and Meanings of Intellectual Property Rights

The Byzantine Empire, when monopolies were given, is where the idea of intellectual property originated. For example, in Greece, chefs were granted a one-year monopoly to capitalise on their recipes. Anyone who created a machine or procedure to speed up the production of silk was granted exclusive privileges by a statutory legislation passed by the Senate of Venice. As a result, after intellectual property was completely foreign to the nomad society, a new period of intellectual property rights protection was granted for all new ideas. One of the categories of intellectual property is copyright. We must understand the idea of intellectual property and its significance before delving into the specifics of copyright and associated challenges in cyberspace. To return home is to step into a space created and brimming with human ingenuity & inventiveness. Everything in our lives, including our carpets and couches, washing machines, refrigerators, and phones, as well as our novels, paintings, and family photos, is a creation of human creativity. Intellectual property refers to the products of the human mind. These days, businesses also use the internet for instructional purposes.

There are two main categories for intellectual property: copyright and industrial property. Patents, trademarks, geographical indications, designs, and designs for semiconductor layouts are all examples of industrial property. Sound recordings, theatrical, artistic, musical, and cinematographic works of art are all protected by copyright. India's main intellectual property laws are the Patents Act of 1970, the Trade Marks Act of 1999, the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act of 1999, the Design Act of 2000, the Semiconductor Integrated Circuits Layout-Design Act of 2000, and the Copyright Act of 1957.

Copyright Concerns in Online Environments

By ensuring that creators of written or visual works have the only authority to copy and distribute their works for the benefit of the public, copyright laws inspire more creative output from these fields. When the copyright period ends, the works are released into the public domain and anybody can copy them without permission. Original works in the fields of literature, theatre, music, painting, film, sound recording, and computer programming are safeguarded by copyright.⁵

These days, copyright benefits a wide range of sectors, such as publishing musical and dramatic compositions for performances, broadcasting, and the creation and distribution of books, periodicals, and newspapers. As intellectual property, copyrights are more swiftly and easily transferred across nations than other types of property. Thanks to advancements in technology, copyright content can now be easily and simply copied. As a result, preventing copyright infringement is extremely challenging and frequently impossible. Books, audio cassettes, videocassettes of movies, or computer programs can be simply moved from one country to another and duplicated in enormous quantities for distribution. Globally, the practice of recording radio and television shows at home without permission has become widespread.⁶

Copyright Violations in Cyberspace

Traditional notions of individual rights and protection are facing formidable challenges in the modern digital age, where it is easy to copy, alter, or simply repeat content from one website to another. Publication is accessible to everybody with a personal computer (PC) and a modem. Everything from downloading to uploading to storing to transforming to making a derivative work is as easy as clicking a button. Because it includes text, images, audio, and video, a web page is copyrighted, much like a book, magazine, or multimedia CD-ROM. The sole party with the authority to authorize the duplication, distribution, or creation of derivative works is the owner of the work, according to copyright laws.⁷

Copyright Law and Computer Software

The Copyright Act defines a computer programme as a "collection of instructions expressed in words, codes, schemes or in any other form, including a machine readable medium, capable of enabling a computer to accomplish a particular task or achieve a particular result" under section 2(ffc). The Copyright Act defines "computer programme" as software.⁸

The Copyright Act further protects this software for computers. The Copyright Act includes computer programs in its definition of literary work. One of the numerous rights that belong to the owner of computer software is the power to grant software licences. Different types of software licenses exist.

Trademark Law in Cyberspace and Issues with Domain Names

"A mark capable of being represented graphically and which is capable of differentiating the goods or services of one person from those of others," according to the definition of a trademark, is everything from the shape of an item to its packaging to the colour combination of it.⁹

A trademark identifies the country of origin of goods. Trademarks serve four objectives, which are described below.

- I. It gives the product's name and place of origin.
- II. It makes a quality assurance.
- III. It promotes the item.¹⁰

It influences the public's opinion of the product, particularly among present or future purchasers. Trademark examples include Sony, Pepsi, Colgate, Pepsi, Lee, and Skoda.

Conflict of Domain Names and Trademarks

In addition to updating and harmonizing trademark laws for products and services, the 1999 Trademark Act sought to limit the use of counterfeit marks. Many trademark owners have found out the hard way that unapproved parties have registered their trademarks as domain names, often with the intent to intentionally violate the rights of the original trademark owner. Domain names are typically registered on a "first come, first served basis," which might result in "abusive registrations," wherein a person or company registers a domain name that contains a trademark without any legitimate right to do so.

Different Types of Trademark Violations in Cyberspace

➤ Cybersquatting

Courts worldwide hear and decide on a large number of domain name disputes. The most severe kind of problem is "cybersquatting," in which an unregistered user or one without inherent rights to the domain uses the name. Some individuals have made a killing by registering domain names that contain other people's trademarks and then selling them to other people or the trademark owners themselves because domain names and trademarks are almost the same thing. What we call "cybersquatting" is actually just sitting on someone else's space. When a person registers a domain name that contains another's name or trademarks, it is referred to as "cybersquatting." This conduct is abusive. Using this strategy, the significance of domain names in establishing a digital identity can be better understood. Whether the goal is to prevent a legal user from registering a highly coveted domain name or to make money off the sale of such names, this well-known approach is often employed. Courts are now looking into the link between trademarks and domain names due to the cybersquatting movement. A successful cybersquatting complaint will show that the domain name is like the brand, that the owner does not have any legal rights or interests in the name, and that the owner's aim was dishonest.¹¹

➤ Using a domain name in reverse

Reverse cybersquatting is another name for this. Cybersquatting is when a trademark proprietor sues a legitimate domain name owner for allegedly attempting to get the domain name through fraudulent means. Domain name owners may be required to surrender ownership to trademark owners to avoid legal action and associated costs in some cases. This is especially true for smaller firms or individuals without the financial means to adequately defend themselves. Famous people, rich people, and large corporations are the usual suspects when it comes to reverse domain name hijacking. Reverse cybersquatting is another name for this. Cybersquatting is when a trademark proprietor sues a legitimate domain name owner for allegedly attempting to get the domain name through fraudulent means. Domain name owners may be required to surrender ownership to trademark owners to avoid legal action and associated costs in some cases. This is especially true for smaller firms or individuals without the financial means to adequately defend themselves. Famous people, rich people, and large corporations are the usual suspects when it comes to reverse domain name hijacking.

➤ Meta tags

This meta tag is one example of a "Meta element" that can be found on web pages. Details on important terms, page descriptions, and other relevant information are included in meta tags. In the early days of the internet, search engines employed meta tags to help sort websites into different categories based on their content and purpose. These days, it's common practice to artificially inflate poorly designed websites' page rankings by manipulating Meta tags. Title, description, and keywords are the three categories of meta tags.

IT, Trademark, and Copyright Act loopholes

At most, cyber-squatters in India can have their domains repossessed, as neither the existing nor the draft Information Technology Act addresses the issue. Despite the absence of any express provision for monetary compensation in the IT Act, IN registration has taken drastic action to compensate affected businesses in an effort to deter would-be domain squatters. Nonetheless, most squatters use obscure monikers. That is, via NIXI, India's National Internet Exchange. The IN Registry is an independent organization whose main function is to maintain the IN-country code top-level domain (cc-TLD) and make sure it's stable, secure, and reliable while it's in use. Full implementation of the new policy has been announced by the Indian government's Department of Information Technology and the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology.

There is a hole in the IT Act concerning jurisdictional issues, cybercrimes involving IP rights, cyberstalking, cyberdefamation, etc. The Copyright Act of 1957 and the Indian Trademark Act of 1999 both fail to address issues pertaining to copyright and trademark infringement in the digital realm. While computer programs are protected by the Copyright Act, there is no recourse for software infringement that occurs online.

Conclusion

An individual's intellectual property is among their most precious possessions because of the effort and skill that goes into creating it. In contrast, stringent legislation is desperately needed in this domain to forestall any future crimes involving intellectual property rights. Domain name purchasers who "in bad faith" acquire domain names that are confusingly close to, or even identical to, registered trademarks or service marks could be able to face legal consequences under the new legislation governing domain name disputes. Trademark owners should consider it a crucial instrument for safeguarding their intellectual property on the internet. The "U.S. Anti-Cybersquatting Consumer Protection Act, 1999" is an unusual statute passed by the US government to address cybersquatting. It safeguards the rights of individuals to prevent the specific use of their personal names in domain names, as well as those of trademark owners to prevent the use of their marks in domain names, whether registered or unregistered. That is why it is so important for India to pass appropriate laws safeguarding the rights of trademark and copyright holders.

The Indian courts are headed in the right direction, but they must ensure that the purpose of these petitions is not undermined or mishandled in the interim. The Delhi High Court ruled in the case of *The Indian Performing Right versus Mr. Badal Dhar Chowdhary CS(OS)1014/2004* that, according to the CPC, such orders cannot be given to the parties while they are acting in their natural location. The court expressed in its entirety that "unclear order can be a manhandle of the procedure of the court and such ambiguous and general order of expectant nature can never be allowed." The application of John Doe orders is another major problem. To prevent misuse, the extent of such requests should be clearly stated. Utilizing John Doe agreements in India has given IP rights holders more awareness and security, however the question remains as to how these demands would be fulfilled. Implementing John Doe orders can include a variety of strategies, such as setting up Commissioners for investigation and seizure and creating new regulations to limit copyright infringement.

Recommendation

India's cybersecurity industry is still in its infancy. Now is the ideal moment to pay attention to concerns related to digital security. Developing mindfulness at the local level, in places like schools, where students can be taught how the Internet works and what risks there are, is anything but difficult. Firewalls should be installed on all corporate PCs, home PCs, and digital cafés. Through their specialised organisations or entryways, clients should be instructed not to interfere with unapproved systems. Strong language should be used to convey the dangers, and the effects should be highlighted. In order to advance the process, cybersecurity awareness should be taught in schools and universities. Legislators must create strong legislation to permit cybersecurity and promote appropriate mindfulness by announcing the same through radio, television, and online advertisements.

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